

D6.1: Initial Dissemination Plan

Author:

Barbara Morganti (MDR)

Contributors:

Kate Fernie (MDR)

Tom Usher (MDR)

Carol Usher (MDR)

All partners

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Table of Contents

1.	Executive summary	4
2.	Objectives	5
3.	Responsibilities for dissemination activities	6
4.	Stakeholder community	7
4.1	Internal stakeholders.....	7
4.2	Small and medium sized institutions	8
4.3	Research community and cloud computing companies / providers	9
4.4	European Commission.....	9
4.5	Clustering with other projects	10
4.6	Groups and associations.....	10
4.7	Stakeholder database	11
5.	Dissemination materials	12
5.1	Project logo.....	12
5.2	Project website	12
5.3	Project newsletter	13
5.4	Other dissemination materials.....	13
5.5	Acknowledgement of EU funding	14
6.	Dissemination channels	15
6.1	Project web site and partners web sites	15
6.2	Mailing lists	15
6.3	Social networks.....	16
6.4	Press releases	17
7.	Dissemination activities	18
7.1	Potential national and international events	18
7.1.1	<i>Potential international events</i>	19
7.1.2	<i>Potential National events</i>	23
7.2	Potential Journals	26
7.2	LoCloud planned events	29
8.	Conclusion	30
9.	Appendix I: Twitter Guidelines	31
10.	Appendix II: Guidelines for partners	32

1. Executive summary

This deliverable presents a dissemination strategy for the **LoCloud project** and it covers months 1 to 24 of the project.

LoCloud will support small and medium-sized institutions in making their content and metadata available to Europeana, by exploring the potential of cloud computing technologies. The project will work on a cloud-based technology infrastructure that will enable the aggregation of local content. It will also develop a number of micro-services to help to reduce technical, semantic and skills barriers and to render the content more discoverable and interoperable.

The aims of the dissemination strategy are to raise awareness about the LoCloud project and its activities amongst:

- Internal stakeholders within the partner organisations
- Organisation with an interest in cloud computing applied to small and medium sized institutions, including small and medium sized cultural heritage institutions, holders of private collections, and others.
- The Research Community with an interest and involvement in cloud computing in general and, applied, in particular, to cultural institutions;
- The European Commission's CIP ICT PSP programme and related projects funded by the programme.
- Europeana, members of the general public, students, researchers, etc.

The initial objectives of the dissemination strategy are to:

- Identify the interests of the stakeholder community and the main channels for communication and networking activities;
- Build and extend the project contact database by clustering with other projects, participation in events and exploiting the partners' networks of contacts;
- Informing the stakeholder community about news, events and activities by developing a project newsletter, exploiting social networking channels as well as traditional media.
- Providing an up-to-date set of dissemination materials by developing the project website, briefing papers, presentation template, and other materials for use by the partners.
- Presenting the project at relevant national and international events.

This plan will be updated at regular intervals and will feed into an Interim dissemination report at months 24 and a Final dissemination report due in at month 36, providing an account of all the dissemination and promotional activities carried out by the project partners throughout the entire project duration.

2. Objectives

LoCloud is co-funded by the European Commission ICT PSP programme, it started on 1st March 2013 and runs for three years. The LoCloud consortium consists of 32 partners from 28 countries.

LoCloud aims to support **small and medium-sized institutions** in making their content and metadata available to Europeana, by exploring the potential of **cloud computing Technologies**.

LoCloud's main goal is to facilitate the role of small and medium-sized institutions by:

- Supporting them in making their content and metadata available to Europeana, by using the cloud to provide services and tools which help to reduce technical, semantic and skills barriers.
- Making available cloud-based software services which enable them to render their content more discoverable and interoperable;
- Enabling smaller institution types such as house museums, which currently fall outside most aggregation infrastructures, to contribute their content to Europeana.
- Exploring the potential of cloud computing for aggregation, enrichment and re-use, with a special focus on geographic location.
- Exploring and trial a cloud based architecture as a scalable platform for Europeana metadata aggregation and harvesting with higher efficiency and reduced maintenance costs.
- Provide guidance, training and support facilities to serve the needs of content providers.

The aim of WP6 (**Dissemination and exploitation**) is to organise a large-scale dissemination effort in order to:

- increase **Europeana's impact at the local level** through a range of activities such as regional, national and international events, online networking and a competition;
- **promote the availability of LoCloud's results** and available services to small and medium sized institutions and to aggregators throughout Europe;
- plan and create **a business model** for a sustainable support service for small and medium sized institutions with limited or no access to the Europeana ecosystem.
- plan with Europeana the way in which the services created by LoCloud can be applied to the whole Europeana corpus in order to **create location-based views** over its entire index.

3. Responsibilities for dissemination activities

WP6 leader is the **University of York - Archaeology Data Service (UoY/ADS)** which is responsible for the following activities:

- coordination of presentations and poster sessions at relevant European and international conferences by project partners, with the purpose of promoting the results of the LoCloud project;
- organisation of a LoCloud workshop at an international conference during year two of the project to promote the goals of the project;
- organisation of a workshop at an international conference during year three to promote the results of the project.

Within WP6, **MDR Partners** is responsible for:

- establishing and maintaining the LoCloud web site(including design of project logo), coordinating the dissemination of news and information about the project through various channels (e.g. web site and social networks);
- preparing a LoCloud newsletter to be published in English twice a year;
- preparing templates for project presentations, documents, briefing papers and other materials;
- establishing a stakeholder database;
- producing an initial dissemination plan, an interim and a final dissemination report.

Finally, MDR Partners together with **National Archives of Norway (NRA)** will be responsible for the organisation of a Europe-wide competition, at the end of the project to stimulate best practice and innovation amongst individual regions, in creating a 'view' in Europeana of the history and heritage of their locality.

All partners are responsible for disseminating information about the project at conferences, events, workshop and via news and social media.

All partners are responsible for naming a dissemination lead person who will be responsible for reporting on dissemination activities, for contributing to the development of the project dissemination plan, Interim and Final Dissemination reports, etc.

4. Stakeholder community

WP6 activities aim to raise awareness about LoCloud and its results amongst the following stakeholders:

- Internal stakeholders within the partner organisations;
- Organisation with an interest in cloud computing applied to small and medium sized institutions, such as small and medium sized cultural heritage institutions, national and domain aggregation services, holders of private collections, Europeana, and others;
- The Research Community with an interest and involvement in cloud computing in general and, applied, in particular to cultural institutions;
- The European Commission's CIP ICT PSP programme and related projects funded by the programme;
- Europeana, end users of Europeana (e.g. students, researchers, etc).

One of the objectives of LoCloud is to improve the interoperability of content from localities across Europe from institutional domains which in some countries act separately: namely the 'heritage' sector and the museums, libraries and archives sectors, in order to provide a more coherent 'view' of the history and heritage of a given locality.

Geographic location is one of the most important aspects of information about local history and archaeological monuments. It offers a means of reconnecting monuments with objects discovered during excavations and now held in museum collections, and with archives, original artworks and publications created by archaeologists, historians, creative writers, artists and ordinary members of the public. The work of LoCloud in this area will contribute to provide end users of Europeana with a gradual but visible improvement in coherence of the 'view' they are able to obtain of the local history of a given locality, often composed of material from a diverse range of sources. All stakeholders, internal and external will substantially benefit from this.

In this connection, the competition that will be organised by LoCloud in the final year, will aim to promote innovative use of the LoCloud services, Europeana API etc. in creating a digital 'view' of the culture of their locality or region. This competition will be aligned within the framework of more general dissemination initiatives conducted by the European Commission and by Europeana.

4.1 Internal stakeholders

Internal stakeholders are one of the target audiences for the LoCloud project as it is important to disseminate to policy makers within the partner organisations, to staff or groups within the organisations to be aware of the projects activities and results and to share the news with their contacts.

Staff within the partner institutions may be interested in news about:

- Progress of project activities
- Results in the more technical area of the project work, e.g.: cloud technologies, metadata, micro-services

- Standards and guidelines
- Releases of new content in Europeana
- Conferences and other events.

The aim of this dissemination activity is to make the subjects aware about LoCloud and its activities and to spread the news to their contacts.

Internal stakeholders will be reached during internal meetings through presentations of the project activities and dissemination of news.

4.2 Small and medium sized institutions

Small and medium sized institutions (e.g. local archives, museums, libraries) are the main target of LoCloud. Many small, local institutions have limited IT infrastructure and lack either the requisite staff skills in digitisation and digital libraries or the organisational capacity to obtain large-scale external funding. Despite this, their collections are important and interesting in the context of Europeana and its users. Increasingly, if gradually, these collections are being made available online and therefore have the potential to contribute to Europeana.

LoCloud will help these institutions in making their content available to Europeana, via developing cloud-based software services and micro-services such as geo-location which are of key importance for local content.

In addition to small and medium sized institutions, the following related stakeholders will be targeted:

- national and domain aggregation services
- holders of private digital collections
- Any other institution with an interest in LoCloud activities and in contributing their content to Europeana.

This community is likely to be interested in:

- Progress of project work
- Specific research outcomes
- Briefing papers providing guidelines and requirements for inclusion of digital collections into Europeana.

LoCloud will interact with these institutions via several channels, including specific surveys to identify digital collections, distribution of news, participation in events, etc.

4.3 Research community and cloud computing companies / providers

This is the community of researchers, and companies and providers who are active in the field of cloud computing for the cultural heritage sector.

The community is likely to be interested in:

- Specific research outcomes
- The technologies and services being developed in LoCloud
- Needs and requirements of the cultural heritage institutions
- Standards and guidelines
- Business models
- Participation in conferences and events.

LoCloud will interact with this stakeholder community by making use of social channels, by disseminating news and by making materials available on the project website.

4.4 European Commission

The European Commission is an important stakeholder in the outcomes of the LoCloud project and represents both an opportunity to disseminate project outcomes to policy makers and also to provide dissemination channels to related projects funded by the programme.

The European Commission, its staff and news channels are likely to be interested in news about:

- The results and outcomes of the project
- Delivery of content to Europeana
- Standards and guidelines
- Evaluation of the results.

The LoCloud project will aim to take advantage of opportunities to present the outcomes at events organised by the European Commission. The LoCloud team will take part in collaboration events organised by the European Commission to share results with other funded projects. These will be also reached through direct contacts, participation in international events and other dissemination channels (see section 6).

4.5 Clustering with other projects

LoCloud's initial plan is to liaise with Europeana Cloud¹, Europeana Creative² and Europeana Inside³. This will be done via exchange of news and other forms of collaborations and, in particular, by the participation in the 'Cloud Coordination Group' organised by Europeana Cloud. The aim of this group is to coordinate those projects working on cloud-based applications for the storage, retrieval and manipulation of metadata and digital content within the context of Europeana.

The first virtual meeting of this group was held in June 2013 and there will be several to follow on a regular basis.

The LoCloud project will also closely collaborate with the 3D ICONS project and will be based on the completed CARARE⁴ project. As a matter of fact, the infrastructural model developed by CARARE and used by 3D ICONS, involving the MINT ingestion service and the MoRe repository, will be the fundamental basis upon which LoCloud's work is being developed.

Naturally, during its entire duration, LoCloud will regularly be in touch with and closely collaborate with Europeana⁵. LoCloud is a member of the Europeana group of projects. The Europeana office maintains the Europeana group web site (<http://group.europeana.eu>) and disseminates information about projects, including LoCloud, to its stakeholder community through the website, a quarterly newsletter and its news channel. The office also maintains a calendar of events informing group members about upcoming events, inviting participation in clustering activities and disseminating information about project's participation in international conferences and events

The LoCloud team will follow the projects identified above and any other related project, via their websites, Twitter and the other social networks.

4.6 Groups and associations

A number of LoCloud partners are members of groups and associations which are active within the field. These groups and associations each represent external networks with resources in place to disseminate news and information with their stakeholders. The strategy for LoCloud will be to explore opportunities to disseminate news and information about project activities with these groups.

¹ <http://pro.europeana.eu/web/europeana-cloud>

² <http://pro.europeana.eu/web/europeana-creative>

³ <http://www.europeana-inside.eu/home/index.html>

⁴ <http://www.carare.eu>

⁵ <http://pro.europeana.eu>

The groups and associations which have been identified so far are:

- WGs of the National Council of Library Coordination
<http://www.mcu.es/bibliotecas/MC/ConsejoCB/Presentacion.html>
- National Association of Archivists and Librarians <http://www.anabad.org/>
- Spanish Federation of Societies of Archivists, Librarians and museum professionals (FESABID) <http://www.fesabid.org/en/introduction-of-fesabid>

More groups and associations will be identified in the course of the project and appropriately used as dissemination channels.

4.7 Stakeholder database

The LoCloud project web site provides a functionality which enables stakeholders from the domain to register to the project's newsletter. This will enable the building of a contact database which will be enlarged throughout the project.

The strategies for building and extending the contact database include clustering with other projects, disseminating news and updates about the project's activities through various channels including direct contacts of partners' network, use of social media, project newsletter, and by participating in conferences and events.

5. Dissemination materials

An initial set of dissemination materials has been produced for the project and includes:

Project logo

5.1 Project logo

The project logo was designed by Carol Usher of MDR Partners and approved by the project consortium.

5.2 Project website

The LoCloud web site (<http://www.locloud.eu/>) was launched in March 2013. The aim of this site is to provide information about the project to stakeholders and to related projects, and also to provide an Intranet for members of the project consortium.

Register Login

LoCloud

About News Resources Activities Community

About LoCloud [Read More](#)

LoCloud is a Best Practice Network co-funded under the CIP ICT-PSP programme of the European Commission which will enrich the Europeana content by adding over 4 million digitised items from European cultural institutions.

Latest News [See All](#)

Jun 05 2013 [Europeana First Free iPad App](#)

May 27 2013 [MTSR 2013](#)

May 19 2013 [Europeana providers](#)

Upcoming Events [See All](#)

Jun 26 2013 [Cultural Heritage, Creative Tools](#)

Jun 27 2013 [IEEE CLOUD 2013](#)

Sep 02 2013 [IPRES-2013](#)

http://www.locloud.eu/rss/feed/my_feed

The public part of the web site includes:

About - the project, consortium and activities

News – news bulletins and newsletter

Resources – presentations, publications, dissemination materials

Activities - Events

Community – links to the social networks.

Contacts

The project Intranet currently includes:

Work packages (one folder for each of the 7 WPs)

Reporting

Reviews

Deliverables.

The web site is initially made available in English. Where appropriate, project partners may provide translations of some parts of the public pages of the site in their national languages.

5.3 Project newsletter

The project newsletter will be produced twice a year. The first one was issued in August and is available from this link: <http://www.locloud.eu/News/Newsletter>.

The Newsletters will be created with a summary newsletter distributed to email lists and with the full newsletter being uploaded to the project website. Notices about the newsletter will be posted on the Social networks and by project partners to their email lists. The motivation behind publishing a summary version of the newsletter with links to the full articles is to send traffic to the project website.

5.4 Other dissemination materials

A basic set of promotional materials is being prepared and made available for use. These materials include:

- A selection of images made available by project partners for use in dissemination materials
- A project fact sheet
- A LoCloud PowerPoint presentation template.

These materials are made available to members of the project for download from the LoCloud website. Additional materials will be made available throughout the life of the project as needs are identified by the dissemination plan.

5.5 Acknowledgement of EU funding

Dissemination materials including reports, presentations, promotional material and publications must clearly acknowledge the EU funding through the inclusion of an appropriate statement and the ICT PSP flag (see below).

Example: "This project is co-funded under the ICT Policy Support Programme (ICT PSP) as part of the Competitiveness and Innovation Framework Programme by the European Community" (ideally with a link to the ICT PSP website: http://ec.europa.eu/ict_psp).

Any communication or publication shall state that it reflects only the author's views and that the European Community is not liable for any use that might be made of the information contained therein.

6. Dissemination channels

LoCloud will use a number of different channels to disseminate information on the project to its stakeholders.

Our strategy is to approach the target audience by making use of social media, professional/personal/local contacts from the project partners' network, etc.

The message to transmit information may vary according to the different target audience, to the phase of the project and to the type of information to promote. While in the initial phase of the project dissemination is more focused on encouraging general awareness about the project, in the course of the project, the emphasis will be more on the promotion of the results and achievements of the project's work.

6.1 Project web site and partners web sites

The project web site is the basic dissemination channel of the project. The web site is managed through a Content Management System (CMS) which allows for flexibility in creating / modifying sections and for publication of information and documentation. The dynamic sections of the site are the News and Events.

All partners are encouraged to disseminate information of LoCloud activities and progress on their own institutional web sites, by regularly posting news and providing links to relevant documentation.

6.2 Mailing lists

The members of the project partners are registered on various mailing lists for professional reasons. These lists cover different subjects in the cultural heritage, research and business domains and have different memberships.

In the coming months partners will be asked to identify which email lists team members are signed up to. A master list will then be made to enable coordination of the project dissemination to these lists, with the aim of guaranteeing coverage and avoiding duplication.

The strategy is to post notices about LoCloud to the lists (for example the newsletter or a forthcoming event with a link to the project website). Such notices are a good way of driving traffic to the web site and allow contacts the opportunity of registering to receive a copy of the Newsletter directly.

The work of sending notices will be done periodically according to the project activities and developments.

The emailing lists which have been identified so far include:

- THEEUROPEANLIBRARY@LIST.ECOMPASS.NL
- EUROPEANA-COMMUNICATORS@LIST.ECOMPASS.NL
- JISCDIGITALMEDIA

- MUSEUMS-INFO (JISC)
- Jisc ADS-ALL
- Foro para profesionales de bibliotecas y documentacion (Forum for library and documentation professionals) (<http://www.rediris.es/list/info/iwetel.html>)
- PUBLICA <http://www.rediris.es/list/info/publicas.html> (public libraries)
- E-learning Special Interest Group Mailing list - ellearn@infoserv.inist.fr
- EDTECH on H-Net - EDTECH@H-NET.MSU.EDU

6.3 Social networks

We consider Twitter a very effective and fast means of dissemination, for its easiness of use and for its immediate outreach which encourages involvement of a large number of users. Our plan is therefore to use this social network as much as possible. LinkedIn will also be used to create and maintain a group of discussion on the most relevant topics concerning LoCloud, Europeana and relevant projects. With regard to Facebook, currently our strategy is to follow the pages on Facebook of other projects (e.g. Europeana Cloud, and Carare) and not to have a Facebook group for LoCloud, which we may decide to create in the future if need arises in the course of the project.

Twitter

The planned strategy for **Twitter**⁶ is to:

- Post tweets related to the project's activities (Newsletter, events, project progresses) or information related to domains of interest to LoCloud.
- Encourage the partners to share interesting news and then tweet them.
- Monitor events (who's attending what events) and tweet about the event with the event hashtag
- Involve LoCloud project members who are active on Twitter to create interest around LoCloud by Tweeting about the project and retweeting any tweets of interest.
- Include the project Twitter feed on the home page of the project website.
- Consider integrating Twitter with LinkedIn to re-post tweets automatically onto LinkedIn: this mechanism would ensure a consistent flow of information and help populate the social networks.
- Follow lists of relevant Twitter users. This activity will give the LoCloud project visibility: some of these users might follow @LoCloudProject in return or retweet LoCloud tweets to their followers etc.

Among the list of relevant Twitter contacts for dissemination we identified so far:

- @Europeanaeu
- @DavidHaskiya - Product developer at Europeana
- @europeana_cloud

⁶ <https://twitter.com/LoCloudProject>

- @EuropeanInside
- @OpenGLAM - OpenGLAM is a global network of people and organisations who are working to open up content and data held by Galleries, Libraries, Archives and Museums.

LinkedIn

The strategy for **LinkedIn** will be to promote discussion about project activities and related themes such as cloud computing, metadata, geographic location, etc. News posted to Twitter will be republished on LinkedIn. The objective will be to increase the number of followers of the group during the year.

A group has been established for LoCloud at: http://www.linkedin.com/groups/LoCloud-4984888?home=&gid=4984888&trk=anet_ug_hm.

Our strategy will be to involve the members in discussions around the project

YouTube

In the course of the project, if appropriate, a **YouTube** channel may be established for LoCloud to enable the publication of videos about the project and its activities.

6.4 Press releases

Press notices and press release are an effective way to disseminate the project outcomes to news media: newspapers or magazines (online or papers versions), news sites, news networks.

A press release was prepared and distributed in March 2013 to announce the start of the project and more press releases will be produced to promote key results of LoCloud.

7. Dissemination activities

7.1 Potential national and international events

LoCloud partners will participate in national and regional workshops, conferences and events in the local heritage and professional domains during the project with the aim of promoting the results of the project and to advocate the contribution of content/metadata to Europeana.

LoCloud will coordinate presentations, poster sessions and workshops at key conferences, for the purpose of promoting the results of the project and the contribution of content to Europeana. It will also be represented at events organised by related projects and at clustering events organised by the Commission.

A series of events have been identified as being relevant to the stakeholder communities targeted by the LoCloud dissemination strategy.

7.1.1 Potential international events

Below the list of conferences that are potential venues for dissemination.

Conference	Link	Description	Location	Dates
ONLINE EDUCA BERLIN	http://www.online-educa.com/	Every year, ONLINE EDUCA BERLIN attracts over 2000 learning professionals from more than 100 countries world-wide, making it the most comprehensive annual meeting place on ICT-enhanced learning and training.	Berlin	December 2014
EC-TEL 2014	http://www.ec-tel.eu	EC-TEL focuses on Technology Enhanced Learning, providing a unique opportunity for researchers, practitioners, and policy makers to discuss current challenges and advances in the field.	TBD	September 2014
International Conference on Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries (TPDL)	http://www.tpd2013.info/	The International Conference on Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries (TPDL) constitutes a leading scientific forum on digital libraries that brings together researchers, developers, content providers and users in the field of digital libraries.	TBD	September 2014
9th edition of the Language Resources and Evaluation Conference (LREC).	http://www.lrec-conf.org/lrec2014/	Organised by ELRA every two years LREC Conferences bring together a large number of people working and interested in Human Language Technologies.	Reykjavik	26-31 May 2014
LINQ 2014 "Learning Innovations and Quality"	http://learning-innovations.eu	LINQ 2014 gathers all experts, practitioners and interested stakeholders in	TBD	May 2014

Conference	Link	Description	Location	Dates
		the fields of lifelong learning, education and training from Europe and all countries		
International Conference on Theory and practice in digital libraries (TPDL). 2014	http://www.wikicfp.com/cfp/program?id=2869&s=TPDL&f=Theory%20and%20Practice%20of%20Digital%20Libraries	A leading scientific forum on digital libraries that brings together researchers, developers, content providers and users in the field of digital libraries.	TBD	2014
Language Technology for Cultural Heritage, Social Sciences, and Humanities (LaTeCH)	Not available yet	The LaTeCH workshop series aims to provide a forum for researchers who are working on developing novel information technology for improved information access to data from the Humanities, Social Sciences, and Cultural Heritage	TBD	2014
International Conference on Technology, Knowledge, and Society in Madrid	http://techandsoc.com/the-conference/call-for-papers	This conference will address a range of topics related to the complex and subtle relationships among technology, knowledge and society.	Madrid, Spain	6-7 February 2014
Media & Learning 2013	http://www.media-and-learning.eu/	Media & Learning 2013 focuses on the latest developments, services and uses of media in education and training. The purpose of this annual event is to identify policies and initiatives that promote digital and media competence at all levels of education and training as well as to promote best-practice in the take-up and application of media in education and	Brussels, Belgium	12-13 December 2013

Conference	Link	Description	Location	Dates
		training.		
GIS Day – open day at the National Heritage Institute	http://www.gisday.com/	An international forum for users of geographic information systems (GIS) technology to demonstrate real-world applications that are making a difference in our society.	Prague, Czech Republic	20 November 2013
ICT 2013	https://ec.europa.eu/digital-agenda/en/ict-2013	A Europe 2020 initiative, the event will focus on Horizon 2020 - the EU's Framework Programme for Research and Innovation for 2014-2020.	Vilnius, Lithuania	6-8 November 2013
International Conference on Vernacular Architecture CIAV2013/7 ^o ATP / VerSus	http://www.esg.pt/ciav2013/index.php/en/enquadramento	Three jointly organised conferences focusing as main topic on Vernacular Architecture.	Vila Nova Cerveira, Portugal	16-20 October 2013
IMCW2013. 4th International Symposium on Information Management in a Changing World	http://imcw2013.bilgiyonetimi.net/	“Beyond the Cloud: Information...Innovation...Collaboration...” being the main theme of the Symposium, IMCW2013 aims to bring together information professionals, computer and information scientists, business people and engineers to discuss the implications of cloud computing on information management and to contemplate on how to design and develop innovative and collaborative information services beyond the cloud.	Limerick, Ireland	4-6 September 2013

Conference	Link	Description	Location	Dates
DC 2013	http://dcevents.dublincore.org/IntConf/dc-2013	DC-2013 will explore questions regarding the persistence, maintenance, and preservation of metadata and descriptive vocabularies	Lisbon, Portugal	2-6 September 2013

7.1.2 Potential National events

Below the list of potential events where LoCloud might be presented on national level.

Event	Link	Description	Location	Dates
VII National Congress of Public Libraries			Madrid	December 2014 (tbc)
National Council of Library Coordination		The event will gather around 100 librarians and policy makers from central and regional administrations in Spain.	Madrid	February/March 2014
APOM-Portuguese Association of Museology Conference		This is the annual conference organised by APOM, the Portuguese Association of Museology.	Lisbon, Portugal	TBD
Skaitmeninė atmintis virtualioje erdvėje 2013" (SAVE2013 - Digital memory in virtual space		Organised by Vilnius universiteto Komunikacijos fakultetas (probably in cooperation with VU Library). This conference mostly targets the professional community of digital humanities or people involved in national/international projects dealing with digital heritage (researchers, librarians, archaeologist, historians, archivists, etc.).	Vilnius, Lithuania	17 December 2013
14th Conference 'Archives, Libraries, Museums in the Digital World'	http://www.skipcr.cz/	A conference targeting professionals from the libraries and museums sectors.	Prague, Czech Republic	November or December 2013

Event	Link	Description	Location	Dates
Meeting of the thematic Commission House-museums - Icom Italia at the National Conference of Icom Italia		The thematic Commission House-museums in Italy was established in 2012 as the representative body of DEMHIST in Italy. The meeting will discuss topics related to house museums conservation, collections management, etc.	Assisi, Italy	22-23 November 2013
Portuguese Association of Librarians and Archivists Congress	http://www.apbad.pt	Annual event of the Portuguese Association of Librarians and Archivists Congress.	Portugal	October 2013
Day of Libraries and Municipalities		It will gather more than 250 librarians and policy makers from the Spanish municipalities.	Madrid, Spain	1 October 2013
Workshop for Reading Past and Present Landscapes 2013	http://readinglandscapesv4.wordpress.com/	It aims to create a platform for an international think-tank exchanging experience and methods of reading historical landscapes. The project involves public institutions, private companies and scientists from Hungary, Czech Republic, Slovakia and Poland. The Workshop is partially funded by the International Visegrad Fund.	Hungary	October 2013
DOMUS Workshop			Madrid, Spain	24-27 September 2013

Event	Link	Description	Location	Dates
ÜNÄK 2013	http://unak2013.unak.org.tr/#	The Turkish University and Research Librarians Association (ÜNÄK) has been organising these annual conferences since 1991. The event focuses on information services, information and record management, knowledge economy, information literacy, etc. The main topic of the 2013 Conference is "Information Systems, Platforms, Architectures and Technologies".	Istanbul, Turkey	19-21 September 2013
Official presentation of the regional organisation of Icom-Italia	http://www.icom-italia.org/	This is an event organised by Icom-Italia the Italian committee of the International Council of Museums (ICOM), which represents museums and museum professionals.	Perugia, Italy	September 2013
X. Slovenská geofyzikálna konferencia	http://gpi.savba.sk/GPIweb/conferences/XSGK2013/XSGK2013.php?op=home	One of the four main topics of this conference is Applied Geophysics - Archaeogeophysics	Smolenice, Slovakia	19-21 August 2013

7.2 Potential Journals

Journal	Country	Link	Description
Historicka revue	Slovakia	http://www.historickarevue.com	A scientific-popular journal about history and archaeology.
Muzeum	Slovakia	http://www.snm.sk/?casopis-muzeum	Guidance, information and study review for museum and art gallery workers.
Naša Univerzita	Slovakia	http://www.uniba.sk/?nu	The Journal of the Comenius University.
Zprávy památkové péče	Czech Republic		Professional journal in Czech language with English and German summary, issued by the National Heritage Institute and focused on heritage and conservation.
Boletín de la Anabad Bulletin of the National Association of Archivists and Librarians	Spain	http://www.anabad.org/publicaciones/boletin.html	Professional journal covering theoretical and practical topics related to archives and libraries.
Delibros Magazine on publishing sector	Spain	http://www.delibros.com/login	Related to the world of publishers, It includes a section on libraries.
Boletín SMS (Somos museos)	Spain		Newsletter of the Unit for the State Museums. It contains news, policies and activities related to Spanish state museums.
Noticias BAD	Portugal	http://www.bad.pt/noticia	Online publication of the Portuguese Association of Librarians, Archivists and Documentalists. It targets professionals working within the archives, libraries and museums fields.
Philobiblon Revue	Romania	http://www.philobiblon.ro/	Transylvanian Journal of Multidisciplinary Research in Humanities

Jlis.it	Italy	http://leo.cilea.it/index.php/jlis/	Italian Journal of Library and information science, is an academic journal of international scope, peer-reviewed and open access, aiming to valorise international research in Library and Information Science.
Almanacco Bibliografico	Italy	http://centridiricerca.unicatt.it/cr/eleb_173.html	quarterly bulletin of the Università Cattolica in Milan related to the history of libraries and books.
Bibliothecae.it	Italy	http://www.bibliothecae.it/index.php?page=abbonamenti	italian half-year journal in history of libraries and books.
AIB Notizie	Italy	http://www.aib.it/pubblicazioni/aib-notizie/	Bimonthly bulletin of Italian libraries Association .
Digitalia. Rivista del digitale nei Beni Culturali	Italy	http://digitalia.sbn.it	Magazine on the application of digital technologies to cultural heritage, published since 2005 by the ICCU.
Information Technology and Libraries	Australia	http://ejournals.bc.edu/ojs/index.php/ital/index	Publishes materials related to all aspects of information technology in all types of libraries. Topic areas include, but are not limited to, library automation, digital libraries, metadata, distributed systems and networks, computer security, intellectual property rights, geographic information systems, and many others.
Archives and Museum Informatics	International	http://www.springer.com/new+%26+forthcoming+titles+%28default%29/journal/10505	Archives and Museum Informatics is an international forum for the representation of knowledge and the management of information relating to the world's cultural heritage. It presents timely, technical contributions to cultural informatics, including theory,

			case studies of implementations, and reviews standards, print and electronic publications, software, network sites and conferences.
ACM Journal on Computing and Cultural Heritage (JOCCH)	International	http://jocch.acm.org/	ACM Journal on Computing and Cultural Heritage (JOCCH) publishes papers of significant and lasting value in all areas relating to the use of information and communication technologies (ICT) in support of Cultural Heritage.
International Journal of Heritage in the Digital Era (IJHDE)	International	http://www.multi-science.co.uk/ijhde.htm	The International Journal of Heritage in the Digital Era (IJHDE) is a quarterly high quality peer reviewed journal in the area of Digital Cultural Heritage, Digital Libraries and Archives.
International Journal for Innovation and Quality and in Learning (INNOQUAL)	International	http://innoqual.efquel.org/	The International Journal for Innovation and Quality and in Learning (INNOQUAL) is an open access, open peer-reviewed journal providing an international perspective on the theory and practice of innovation and quality in the field of learning at all educational levels and in all training contexts. It seeks contributions which discuss how technology can contribute to innovate and enhance the quality of learning.
International Journal of the Inclusive Museum	International	http://onmuseums.com/publications/journal	The International Journal of the Inclusive Museum brings together academics, curators, museum and public administrators, cultural policy makers and research students to engage in discussions about the historic character and future shape of the museum. The key question of the Journal is: How can the institution of the museum become more inclusive?

7.2 LoCloud planned events

Meeting/event	Date (Project month)	Participants	Location
Content provider workshops (3)	MM6-7: 29-30 Aug; 12-13 Sept; 19-20 Sept	All participants	Copenhagen, York, Madrid
Plenary meeting	M9: 28-29 Nov	All participants	London
Mid-term plenary meeting	M18	All participants	South or Eastern Europe (tbd)
Regional training workshops	M22	Selected partners	Tbd
Workshop at international conference	M18-24	Selected partners	Tbd
Workshop at international conference	M24-36	Selected partners	Tbd
Technical reviews	M12, M24 & M36	Project management team, WP leaders	Tbd
Final conference and awards	M34-36	Up to 200 external stakeholders, plus project participants	Tbd

8. Conclusion

This document presents the dissemination strategy of the LoCloud project for the first two years of the project.

In the first year of the project dissemination activities will focus on the raising awareness about the project in national and international contexts.

This dissemination plan will be updated by month 24 to produce the Interim Dissemination Report.

9. Appendix I: Twitter Guidelines

Guidelines for Tweeting About the LoCloud Project

MDR is managing the Twitter account of the LoCloud project (@LoCloudProject).

The LoCloud project members are invited to Tweet about the project or retweet any tweets of interest.

In order to make the best use of Twitter for the Project the following guidelines will be of help:

1. Target audience The prime focus should be people from Cultural Heritage organisations/institutions, especially small and medium sized institutions. After this, it should be aimed at professionals (not necessary working in the field on Cultural Heritage) involved in /with experience in cloud computing technologies.

2. Objectives for Twitter:

- a. Keep key followers informed of LoCloud activities (progress made, publications, upcoming events etc.)
- b. Inform followers about topics/issues of interest that are related to LoCloud.

3. Achieving the objectives:

- a. Informing followers about new content on the LoCloud web site and LinkedIn.
- b. Informing followers about topics/issues of interest that are related to LoCloud (i.e. upcoming conferences/prizes/info days/calls/research areas/innovations/studies)

4. Tweets posted: Twitter only allows tweets of 140 characters or less, tweets should include a link with a title (to effectively communicate the message) and in some cases use a more confidential tone.

5. LoCloud follows – people who are related to the target audience and professionally involved in cloud computing and cultural heritage. We do not follow people whose tweets are of a personal nature. We will periodically review and 'unfollow' the less useful tweeters to make monitoring the feeds more manageable.

6. Tweeting: it would be useful to Tweet at least once a fortnight

7. Reply: The LoCloud account will reply to specific tweets directed at @LoCloud (asking questions or feedback about the project).

LoCloud Project members (and followers):

- remember to use the hash tag when you are tweeting about the project: #LoCloud
- Please Retweet any tweets that may of interest to your friends and colleagues

10. Appendix II: Guidelines for partners

Guidelines for partners of LoCloud regarding their dissemination activities

Where to find LoCloud promotional materials

Dissemination materials for use by LoCloud partners are available in the Partners area of the web site, under WP6, at:

<http://www.locloud.eu/Partner-Area/WP6-Dissemination-and-exploitation>

This section will be regularly updated throughout the project.

Where to disseminate information about LoCloud

All project partners are requested to promote LoCloud whenever possible, namely:

- on their institutional website
- at national and international events (organised by their own institutions, by other institutions, by Europeana, or by other Europeana group projects, etc.)
- at relevant professional fairs and exhibitions.

Production of customised promotional materials

Partners who wish to produce customized promotional material for dissemination in their country (for example, in the language of their country) can do that using their own budget.

Note that all produced dissemination materials should comply with the corporate image of the project and that before producing any materials partners should first inform MDR.

All project dissemination materials must clearly acknowledge the EU funding through the inclusion of an appropriate statement and the EU flag (see paragraph 5.5).

Informing and reporting on your dissemination activities

Before the event:

Each partner should inform UoY/ADS and MDR of any event they plan to attend indicating the name of the event, dates location, URL and planned contribution (e.g. presentation, poster session, etc.).

This will enable the LoCloud management to better coordinate dissemination activities, avoiding overlaps and WP6 leaders to promote the event and the partner's contribution on the project web site and other dissemination channels.

Partners are also expected to promote their dissemination efforts on their own web sites, via project and professional mailing lists, personal contacts, social networks, press releases, etc.

After the event:

All partners should report on their dissemination activities via using the reporting template provided by Geoff Butler (MDR) which includes a section on dissemination (available in the Partner area of the project web site at: <http://www.locloud.eu/Partner-Area/Reporting>).

Partners are also encouraged to send their delivered presentations (in pdf format), audios, videos, images, or any other related materials to Barbara Morganti (barbara.morganti@mdrprojects.com) for publication on the LoCloud website.